

Chloride Ion Determination by Mohr's Method in Dilute Acid Medium

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The soluble chloride content in reinforced concrete, particularly those exposed to saline environment, is an important parameter to assess anticorrosion property¹. Usually water extract of powder concrete sample is analysed for soluble chloride content by Mohr's method using K_2CrO_4 as indicator. Due to simplicity of this method, it is widely used to analyse chloride content of water and chemicals². Mohr's method is exclusively applicable in neutral or slightly alkaline solution (pH 6.5–10)³. The water extract of a concrete sample is neutralised with HNO_3 , and the excess acid is neutralised by the addition of chloride-free $CaCO_3$ or $NaHCO_3$. The addition of $CaCO_3$ serves two purposes—it neutralises the excess acid and increases contrast to visualise clearly the end-point. Here we have attempted to show how much excess acid can be tolerated in Mohr's method, i.e. without addition of $CaCO_3$. This will help use of Mohr's method to determine chloride in acid medium upto a certain pH. A parallel spectrophotometric study of the solution has also been performed.

Results and Discussion

The results of chloride ion determination are summarised in Table 1. The data show that clear end-point is detectable upto 1.2 ml 0.2 N HNO_3 , i.e. upto pH 5.44. Below this pH the CrO_4^{2-} is converted to $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$, and the solubility product of $Ag_2Cr_2O_7$ being high remains soluble⁴. The colour change with addition of acid, from yellow to brown is due to conversion of CrO_4^{2-} to $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ (Ref. 5).

These could be explained by considering the conversion equilibrium, $CrO_4^{2-} \rightleftharpoons HCrO_4^- \rightleftharpoons Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ in

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CHLORIDE ION IN DILUTE HNO_3 MEDIUM

0.01 N NaCl = 5 ml, K_2CrO_4 soln added = 1 ml

Sl no	0.2 N HNO_3 added ml	0.01 N $AgNO_3$ * reqd ml	pH of mixture before titration	Colour change yellow to	Remark**
1	0	5.2	7.92	—	GA
2	0.2	5.2	—	—	GA
3	0.4	5.3	6.58	light brown	GA
4	0.6	5.2	—	light brown	GA
5	0.8	5.2	6.11	deep brown	GA
6	1.0	5.3	5.75	deep brown	GA
7	1.2	5.3	5.44	deep brown	GA
8	1.3	NEP	5.33	brown to yellow	NA
9	1.4	NEP	—	brown to yellow	NA

*0.2 ml 0.01 N $AgNO_3$ required in blank titration, NEP= no end-point

**GA = good agreement, NA = not applicable

acid medium. A change of pH values has been checked stepwisely for the 6th experiment (Table 1), viz. (i) 5 ml 0.01 N NaCl + 1 ml 0.2 N HNO_3 , pH = ~1.45; (ii) solution (i) diluted to 50 ml, pH = ~2.5, (iii) 5 ml 0.01 N NaCl + 1 ml K_2CrO_4 (5%) + 43 ml water + 1 ml 0.2 N HNO_3 , pH = ~5.75. A pH jump from ~2.5 to ~5.75 is due to use up of H^+ ions. From 0.2 to 1.2 ml N HNO_3 in solution, this use up process of H^+ ions goes on with gradual deepening of colour of the solution. K_2CrO_4 is 0.258 molar. In 50 ml solution

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CrO_4^{2-} content is 5.16×10^{-3} mol in each case. But H^+ ion content (in absence of CrO_4^{2-}) varies from 8×10^{-4} to 5.2×10^{-3} mol for 0.2 to 1.3 ml of 0.2 *N* HNO_3 in 50 ml respectively.

The H^+ reacts with CrO_4^{2-} in solution as $\text{CrO}_4^{2-} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{HCrO}_4^-$; $\text{HCrO}_4^- + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4$; $2\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4 \rightleftharpoons \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Each CrO_4^{2-} ion takes up two H^+ ions for $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ formation. At lower volumes of HNO_3 (0.2–1.2 ml), $[\text{H}^+]$ in solution is less than the $[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]$ and partially HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ are formed and excess $[\text{CrO}_4^{2-}]$ remains in solution. At 1.3 ml HNO_3 , $[\text{H}^+] \approx [\text{CrO}_4^{2-}] \approx 5.16 \times 10^{-3}$ mainly HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ exist in solution and at further higher volume of HNO_3 mainly $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ is formed. However, so long CrO_4^{2-} remains in solution in equilibrium with HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, on addition of cation (Ag^+) which forms insoluble chromates, the chromates and not dichromates are precipitated. The equilibria shift to the left due to separation of insoluble chromate from solution. The above equilibria are applicable in HNO_3 and HClO_4 media. In higher acid concentration Ag_2CrO_4 dissolves due to solubility of $\text{Ag}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$.

The result is further supported by uv spectral analysis (Table 2). The decrease in absorbance value from 2.9 to 0.963 at λ_{max} 372–368 nm is perhaps due to decrease in concentration of CrO_4^{2-} . Further, the change of λ_{max} from 372 to 368 nm indicates the interference in absorbance of CrO_4^{2-} by HCrO_4^- and $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$. At higher concentration of HNO_3 (1.3 ml onwards), $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ predominates ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 349\text{--}350 \text{ nm}$)⁶.

In order to justify the applicability of Mohr's method at pH 5.44, soluble chloride contents in reinforced concrete and in water sample (Ganga Canal, Roorkee) have been determined following the present procedure. They are in good agreement with the experimental results at pH 7 (Table 3).

It appears that the Mohr's method for quantitative determination of chloride ion can be successfully employed upto pH 5.44 without addition of CaCO_3 . The present study reports the applicability of the

Mohr's method in a solution of one order higher acid concentration; the so far reported lower limit was pH 6.5 (Ref. 3).

TABLE 2—UV SPECTRAL DATA

Sl. no.	Soln. composition			λ_{max} nm	ϵ
	K_2CrO_4 ml	HNO_3 ml	Water ml		
1.	1	0.0	19.0	372	2.9114
2.	1	0.2	18.8	370	2.6952
3.	1	0.4	18.6	369	2.3358
4.	1	0.8	18.2	368	1.7057
5.	1	1.2	17.8	369	0.9630
6.	1	1.3	17.7	350	1.1552
7.	1	1.4	17.5	349	0.9638

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF CHLORIDE ION AT pHs 5.44 AND 7

Sample**	%Cl determined with Mohr's method	
	pH 7	pH 5.44
RC-1	1.50 (0.012)	1.51 (0.013)
RC-2	0.82 (0.012)	0.82 (0.015)
RC-3	0.67 (0.012)	0.67 (0.012)
RC-4	0.43 (0.013)	0.44 (0.015)
RC-5	0.32 (0.012)	0.32 (0.012)
Water	0.24 (0.013)	0.24 (0.012)

* Average value calculated from 5 sets of analysis and standard deviation in parenthesis.

** For RC (reinforced concrete) samples only mortar portion taken and chloride ion extracted with distilled water, and data reported in percent on the basis of cement content.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used. HNO_3 (0.2 *N*), NaCl (0.01 *N*) an 5% (w/v) potassium chromate solutions were prepared. Double-distilled water was used all through.

An Electrotech pH meter was used.

Chloride ion determination by Mohr's method in slightly acid medium : A mixture of 0.01 *N* NaCl (5 ml) and K_2CrO_4 solution (1 ml) was diluted with water to ~ 50 ml. To each of a set of ten (10) such solutions, various amounts (0.2 to 1.5 ml) of 0.2 *N* HNO_3 was added separately and the mixtures were titrated with 0.01 *N* AgNO_3 solution. After addition of HNO_3 in each case the colour change was also observed.

Following the same procedure, the soluble chloride content of a number of reinforced concrete

(exposed in saline water) and a sample of water (Ganga Canal, Roorkee) were determined at pH 5.44 and also at pH 7 (adjusted by adding NaHCO_3) for reference and comparison.

The change of CrO_4^{2-} to $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ by stepwise addition of HNO_3 was studied through uv-absorption, recorded with a Hitachi 3200 spectrophotometer. K_2CrO_4 and HNO_3 solutions used in titration were diluted 20 times to get absorption within the scale of the instrument.

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